

THE ISSUE OF CATALOGING IN THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF
ASOMIDDIN URINBOEV

Burkhanov Ilyaskhan Mukhiddinovich,
PhD student of Fergana State University

Abstract: The article analyzes the issues of source studies and resource cataloging in Uzbekistan from the point of view of A. Orinboev's scientific activity.

Key words: Catalogue, source, history, ideology, oriental manuscripts

The issue of cataloging and classification of oriental manuscripts is of great importance in the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Orinboev. He actively participated in the creation and publication of seven catalogs of the source fund of the Institute of Oriental Manuscripts under the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan. In addition, he managed to create and publish a catalog based on five foreign projects at the international level. In the analysis of the scientist's achievements in this field, the history of the catalog and its creation was briefly discussed.

The word catalog is defined as follows: "Catalog - (Greek katalogos list) means a list of certain items, such as books, exhibits, products, given in a certain order. For example, stamps, works of art, a library catalog, a place where file names are stored in the logical device of computer programs, a collection of files. can be said to have created the catalog.

The oldest catalog that has survived to this day is a collection of documents collected by Ashurbanipal of Assyria in the 7th century BC. Language, summary of the text, title, author's name, code of the library where the document is stored, i.e. number are written on each of its plates [2.1.]. One of the interesting facts about the wall catalog: it was recorded on the wall of the building about the funds

of the library of the Temple of Horus, founded in 239 BC. To some extent, the study of these data helps in the research of the scientific heritage of Asomiddin Orinboev. The catalogs compiled and edited by the scientist were able to combine ancient experience and new science. The catalogs are in the form of a thick book, with several descriptions written for each source, the date the source was written and copied by the calligrapher, whether there is another copy of it, the quality of the paper on which the manuscript was copied and the quality of the paper on which it was copied, in some cases even the place of production of the paper, the number it is stored in. given in detail. In scientific news, on the initiative of Asomiddin Orinboev, the sources of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the UzR FA began to be cataloged [3.1.10].

G. Karimov had great difficulty in finding a unique source and "Cataloging of manuscripts, i.e. compiling a brief description of works in manuscript books and publishing them in the form of books, has been one of the most important scientific tasks of this institution since 1943, when the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Abu Rayhan Beruni of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan was established [4.1.B.131-132].", he noted. In doing so, he pointed to the ease with which every researcher can easily find and use the desired source with the help of the catalog. Because he said that he could not find the necessary source even in foreign countries, and that it was difficult to find it in Uzbekistan using the catalog. Asomiddin Orinboev is commendable for facilitating the work of such researchers and scientists and organizing existing manuscripts. But although such work is actually a complex process, for a person looking from the outside, these efforts are not noticeable. Let's imagine that if there is no catalog, one can spend several months to find a single source among more than eleven thousand manuscripts. Based on the directory, you will have that resource in five minutes. Only a person who has gone through this process can deeply understand how convenient and light it is, and appreciate the work of the scientists who compiled the catalog and prepared it for publication.

Academician D. Yusupova was also interviewed several times regarding the issue of cataloging of manuscripts by Asomiddin Orinboev. "Before Uzbekistan gained independence, an 11-volume catalog was published based on the sources available in the manuscript fund of our Institute of Oriental Studies. Theirs Volumes V and VI were prepared by Aka Asomiddin himself with descriptions. [3.2.B.9.]" Currently, these catalogs are almost not used in scientific circulation. Because, after independence, they were published in a new and convenient way. Nevertheless, based on the research objective, the eleven-volume catalog was thoroughly studied.

According to Professor A. Semenov, when writing the descriptions of the manuscripts included in volume V prepared for publication in 1960, S.A. Azimjonova, V.I. Belyaev, E. Betger, D. Voronovsky, V. Zhukov, A. Qayumov, A. Kononov, N Mikluho-Maklay, A. Molchanov, K. Munirov, T. Nigmatov, Z. Rizaev, M. Sale, A. Semenov, O. Smirnova, K. Starkova, S. Tveritina, A. Orinboev, A. Shmitlar actively participated [5.1.B.8.].

The fifth volume of the catalog includes sections entitled history, biography (biographical score), act and epigraphy, memoirs and fiction, each of which contains a classification of manuscripts related to the field.

According to the scientist D. Voronovsky, who wrote the introduction to volume VI of Eastern manuscripts published in 1963, the descriptions of fifty-two manuscripts included in this collection were written by Asomiddin Orinboev [6.1.B.10]. Thirty-two of them were included in the catalog with repetition, and as a result, 84 descriptions belonged to Asomiddin Orinboev.

In 1964, the VII volume of the aforementioned catalog was published under the editorship of candidate of historical sciences Asomiddin Orinboev and candidate of philological sciences L.M. Epifanovalar. The description of the manuscripts included in this collection was prepared by A. Qayumov, K. Munirov, T. Nigmatova, A. Orinboev. A total of 608 manuscripts are described in it, most of them belong to the literary literature of the XIV-XX centuries. Manuscripts in the

poetry department are works of the 14th-20th centuries, and among their authors there are literary representatives such as Navoi, Lutfiy, Sakkokiy, Durbek [6.1.B.8].

Reference:

1. Флоров Ю. Из истории библиотечных каталогов //Наука и жизнь. № 6. – Россия, 2022. Батафсил маълумот учун қаранг: <https://www.nkj.ru/archive/articles/44638/>
3. Юсупова Д. Асомиддин Уринбаев. – Ташкент, 2004. – С. 11
3. Хатамова, З. (2021). Expenditure of income from taxes and levies in the kokand khanate: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In *research support center conferences* (No. 18.05).
4. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2022). SH. VOKHIDOV'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE KOKAND KHANATE. *Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects*, 139-141.
5. Xatamova, Z. (2021, June). EXPENDITURE OF INCOME FROM TAXES AND LEVIES IN THE KOKAND KHANATE. In *Конференции*.
6. Хатамова, З. (2023). Из истории денежной политики в финансовой системе Коканского ханства. *Актуальные проблемы истории Узбекистана*, 1(1), 327–336. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/history-of-uzbekistan/article/view/16511>
7. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2022). Political-Financial Analysis of the Issues of Science of the Kokand Khanate in the Work of Khudoyorkhonzade “Anjum At-Tavorikh”. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, 3(10), 102-111. Retrieved from <https://cajssh.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJSSH/article/view/463>
8. Burkhonov, I. M. (2020). “ZAKAT” HAS ENSURED FAIRNESS AND BALANCE IN SOCIETY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 201-204.
9. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2020). Negative impact of the tax system on political life on the example of the history of the Kokand Khanate (1850–

1865). *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(5), 790-795.

10. Burkhonov, I. (2021, June). The importance of the scientific heritage of asomiddin urinboev in the study of the history of the Kokand khanat. In *Конференции*.

11. Burkhonov, I. (2021). The importance of the scientific heritage of asomiddin urinboev in the study of the history of the Kokand khanat: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1242>. In *RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES* (No. 18.05).

12. Бурханов, И. (2023). Научное наследие Шарафиддина Али Язди в интерпретации Асомиддина Оринбоева. *Актуальные проблемы истории Узбекистана*, 1(1), 165–171.

13. BURKHONOV, I. FROM THE HISTORY OF THE TRANSLATION OF THE WORK OF ABURAZZAK SAMARKAND" MATLA'I SA'DAYN AND MAJMA'I BAHRAIN. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 138-144.

14. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2022). The Importance of Asomiddin Urinboev's Scientific Research in the Study of the History of the Kokan Khanate. *Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research*, 3, 175-179.

15. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2022). In the Study of the History of the Kokand Khanate. *Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics*, 6, 68-71.

16. Burkhanov, I. (2022). FROM THE HISTORY OF THE USE OF THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF KOKAND SCIENTISTS ASOMIDDIN URINBOEV. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 2(10), 63–67.

17. Хатамова, З. (2021, August). EXPENDITURE OF INCOME FROM TAXES AND LEVIES IN THE KOKAND KHANATE: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In *RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES* (No. 18.05).

- 18.Хатамова, З. Н. Особенности налоговой системы Кокандского ханства / З. Н. Хатамова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2020. — № 5 (295). — С. 254-256. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/295/66918/>
- 19.Nazirjonovna, H. Z., & Abdumannobovich, N. M. (2020). Tax system on the territory of kyrgyzstan during the Kokand Khanate. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 209-212.
- 20.Xatamova, Z. (2020). Expenditure of state funds replenished by taxes in the history of the kokand khanate. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 5(3), 274-277.
21. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. ., & Odinakhan, A. . (2023). PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS AND THEIR TYPES. *JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING*, 2(5), 18–21.
22. Khatamova, Z. N., & Almatatova , N. (2023). SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(9), 19–23
- 23.Nazirjonovna, K. Z. ., & Abduvaxitovich, A. A. . (2023). APPLICATION OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION AND ITS FUTURE . *IJTIMOY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(5), 98–104.
24. Sh. Kholmatov. (2023). THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUALITY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF CIVIL SOCIETY. *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 16, 430–436.
- 25.АРАББОЕВ, Х. PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE UPBRINGING OF THE PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF THEIR STUDENTS. THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE FORMATION OF READING.
- 26.Араббоев, Х. Х. (2022). ЎҚУВЧИЛАРНИ ОММАВИЙ СПОРТ СОҒЛОМЛАШТИРИШ ЖАРАЁНИГА ТАЙЁРЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-ПЕДАГОГИК ЗАРУРАТИ. *Science and innovation*, 1(В3), 378-385.

27. N.Mamirov. (2022). YURTIMIZDA KURASH SPORT TURINING RIVOJLANISHI VA YOSHLAR HAYOTIDAGI O'RNI. *Journal of Integrated Education and Research*, 1(7), 317–321.
28. Ибрагимов Наврўзбек Кимсанбаевич, Рустамов Илхомиддин Абдукодирович, Хатамова Зумрадхон Назиржоновна, Бурхонов Илёсхон Муҳиддинович. (2023). ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИНИ РАҚОБАТДОШЛИГИНИ БОШҚАРИШДА БИТИРУВЧИЛАРНИ ИШ БИЛАН ТАЪМИНЛАШ МАСАЛАСИ. *SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IDEAS IN MODERN EDUCATION*, 1(7).
29. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. ., & Abduvaxitovich, A. A. . (2023). APPLICATION OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION AND ITS FUTURE . *IJTIMOIIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI*, 3(5), 98–104.
30. Khatamova, Z. N., & Almatamova , N. (2023). SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(9), 19–23.
31. Khatamova Zumradkhon Nazirjanovna. (2022, май 19). COVERING THE EMBASSY ISSUES OF THE KOKAND KHANATE IN HISTORICAL SOURCE "ANJUM AT-TAVORIX". INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, Washington, USA. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564783>
32. Xamdamova O.M., Xatamova Z.N., Ibragimov N., Tishabaeva I. (2023). O'ZBEKISTON TA'LIMIDA UZVIY BOG'LIQLIK VA RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI. *SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IDEAS IN MODERN EDUCATION*, 1(7).
33. Kholmatov, S. (2023). STUDYING THE PROBLEM OF SOCIAL ADAPTATION OF STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. *B INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (T. 3, Выпуск 10, сс. 468–471)*.

34. Sh. Kholmatov. (2023). *THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUALITY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF CIVIL SOCIETY*. *European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development*, 16, 430–436.
35. Mamirov Nasirjon. (2023). *THE ISSUE OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN ENGAGEMENT IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION*. *International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*. Finland Academic Research Science Publishers, 11(10), 395–400.
36. Arabboyev, H. (2023). *THE SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL NEED OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR THE PROCESS OF HEALTHY SPORTS*. *International Conference On Higher Education Teaching*, 1(11), 23–28.
37. Xamdamova, O., & Husaynova, M. (2023). *ILMIY USLUBNING LEKSIK-GRAMMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI*. *Молодые ученые*, 1(15), 140-142.
38. Xamdamova, O., & Husaynova, M. (2023). *KICHIK HAJMLI MATNLARNING LINGVOSTILISTIK XUSUSIYATLARI*. *Молодые ученые*, 1(15), 135-139
39. Husaynova, M. (2023). *CERTAIN STYLES EXPRESSED IN UZBEK ANECDOTES EVENTS*. *International Conference on Management, Economics & Social Science*, 1(8), 18–21.
40. Husaynova, M. (2023). *LATIFALAR MATNLARIDA FONOSTILISTIK VOSITALARNING IFODALANISHI*. *Молодые ученые*, 1(15), 143-146.
41. Tashlanova, H. D. (2019). *Развитие критического мышления студентов в вузах. Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (11-2 (144)), 63-64.
42. Tashlanova, N. (2021). *The essence of collaborative approach in learning a language*. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 281-286.
43. Akbarova, N. A. (2023). *MUSTAQILLIK YILLARIDA FARG ‘ONA VILOYATI MUSIQA MAKTABLARI FAOLIYATI: YUTUQLAR VA MUAMMOLAR*. *Interpretation and researches*, 1(1).
44. Husaynova, M., Xamdamova, O., Tishabaeva, I., Xatamova, Z., & Ma’rufjon, G. K. H. M. (2023). *LATIFALAR MATNINING FONOSTILISTIK*

XUSUSIYATLARI. SCIENCE AND PEDAGOGY IN THE MODERN WORLD:
PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS, 1(9).

45.Хамдамова О.М., Хатамова З.Н., Ибрагимов Н., Тишабаева И.
(2023). УЗБЕКИСТОН ТАЛИМИДА УЗВИЙ БОГЛИКЛИК ВА
РИВОЙЛАНТИРИШ УСУЛЛАРИ. *НАУЧНЫЕ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ
ИДЕИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ*, 1 (7). Получено с
<http://woconferences.com/index.php/SIIME/article/view/689>.

46.И.Тишабаева, З.Хатамова, Н.Ибрагимов,
О.Хамдамова. (2023). УЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРИКСИ ФАНЛАРИНИ
О'КИТИШДА ЗАМОНАВИЙ ПЕДАГОГИК ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРДАН
ФОЙДАЛАНИШ МАСАЛАЛАРИ. *НАУЧНЫЕ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ
ИДЕИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ*, 1 (7). Получено с
<http://woconferences.com/index.php/SIIME/article/view/690>.